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Welcome to our second newsletter!

In this edition we bring you news of our recent virtual Data Stewardship events, details of our working groups and we have two more student profiles plus our first instructor profile, Raphael Cbe - make sure to read about Raphael's forthcoming webinar and please let us know what topics you would like covered in future webinars.

If you have attended one of the CODATA/RDA Schools for Research Data Science but haven't yet completed [the form](#) - to be included in our interactive world visualisation map highlighting where all our alumni come from - please do so! The map will soon to be released and visible on our [website](#).

Data Stewardship Training

University of Manchester

In November a Data Steward training event was co-organised by Research Data Management staff at the University Library and our team of instructors in collaboration with the EU network FAIRsFAIR. The purpose of the training was to introduce the concept of data stewards to The University of Manchester as a pilot programme in the first stage of the University's new Research Data Management Strategy, and in conjunction with the institution-wide Research Lifecycle Programme. The model used was a 'train the trainer' approach, whereby a small group of 12 participants took part, drawn from Library Research Services, Library Digital Technologies and Services, Research IT, Information Governance, and data managers already embedded within schools and faculties.

The training aimed to bring together data management and open research perspectives from across the Professional Services involved in the day-to-day processes of research data management.

As this was the first online iteration of the CODATA-RDA Research Data Summer School involving new participants, the curriculum was streamlined to focus on a few key topics which would be of most use to the chosen cohort. The training was delivered via an online discussion forum where slides and exercises were posted, and via three one-hour virtual sessions.

This introduction to data stewardship will now assist the development of the RDM strategy at The University of Manchester: how we build upon current good

Universidad Nacional, Costa Rica

Correspondingly this Foundational Data Steward workshop took place in December. The event was very important for the University as it allowed the participants to train and update themselves in terms of management of research data and other aspects related to good practices in the use of their data. “The work of the Research Data Science Schools has been fundamental to accompany this process in which various sectors of the university such as librarians, computer scientists, researchers from all areas, academic advisors and journal editors are sharing information and creating a common notion of what is the type of data policy we need and how to approach it”. Paola Gonzalez Vargas.

Participant comments:

- “It is extremely important to clarify concepts, and see the practical usefulness of the concepts in our reality as a university.”

-“With this training It was evident that some of the tasks that we have been doing with the repositories are related to the tasks of a Data Stewardship. We can work on some more things from this area.“

Working Groups

Eight Working Groups have been set up within the CODATA-RDA Schools for Research Data Science. These Groups propose actions and implementation plans to be approved by the co-chairs. Once approved they may be asked to be part of the Implementation Team which will implement changes in the project based on solutions proposed by the Working Groups.

WG1 Curriculum Evolution

Seeks to keep the schools updated with new directions in technology. Each class will have at least one member responsible for updating the class outline once a year. This outline should guide the school instructors but it should also be open to suggestions from them. This WG would also build on synergies with academic programmes.

WG2 Sustainability and Funding

The value of the CODATA-RDA Summer Schools has been proven over the past 5-years of events and the leadership group has shown long-term commitment and effort toward the future of the group. We will be gathering a group of experts to form a working group to provide the schools with direction and strategic planning for the long-term sustainability of future events. This group’s objective is to keep in touch

communication with regular sponsors.

WG3 Train the Trainer

This group's objective is to keep in touch with the school instructors and find sustainable ways to create, build and maintain human resources. Each member is encouraged to look for new instructors each year, and to maintain good communication with regular instructors and helpers.

WG 4 Events in Africa and Europe

This group will have the responsibility to organise future events in Africa and Europe. Each member must know the basic requirements for a host institution, and at least one will serve as contact and director for each event, having all the responsibilities listed in the Manual for Co-chairs.

WG 5 Events in the Americas

This group will have the responsibility to suggest new locations, recruit additional instructors from the region, make the first contact with local hosts, and organise future events in the Americas. Each member must know the basic requirements for a host institution, and at least one will serve as contact and director for each event, having all the responsibilities listed in the Manual for Co-chairs.

WG 6 Events in Asia and Australasia

This group will have the responsibility to organise future events in Asia and Australasia. So far there has only been a one week version of the school that was held in Brisbane and hence this represents a gap in the delivery of the schools, particularly as the long term vision sees the delivery of schools across all regions. This group would prioritise potential partners/locations, recruit (if necessary) additional instructors and in collaboration with the co-chairs and the Sustainability Working Group identify funding for the events. Each member must know the basic requirements for a host institution, and at least one will serve as contact and director for each event, having all the responsibilities listed in the Manual for Co-chairs.

WG 7 Communication and External Messaging

This group will take care of the communication platform for all the schools. This includes creating videos, art and posts to publicise the schools, as well as to keep (and provide content for) the Schools webpage and social media updated and regularly check the school hashtags for content.

WG8 Alumni

The summer schools have entered into their 5th year, and to date have trained over 450 students from around 40 countries. This growing body of international researchers is a key asset for the schools, and one that we are very enthusiastic to foster. In order to do so, we have created an alumni network. Through this network we aim to foster an identity amongst our students as CODATA-RDA schools alumni. This will contribute two key benefits. First, it will create an active pool of researchers who will contribute to future schools, CODATA and RDA activities. Alumni are the base of our model to keep updating instructors, helpers, directors, and co-chairs, and

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draw on to advance their personal research goals.

The alumni working group is always looking for interested individuals to join our activities. We also welcome suggestions for activities and speakers for the webinars. Please feel free to contact us if you'd like to get involved.

Instructor Profile

Raphael C6be

I live in Sao Paulo and work as a Research Associate at the Center for Scientific Computing at the Sao Paulo State University, where I work together with a team of particle physicists inside the CMS LHC collaboration doing data analysis, trying to tackle the challenges in finding evidence of physics beyond the standard model. The usage of computer science tools to solve basic science problems has always amused me and that is what I've been trying to do since I finished my PhD on Artificial Intelligence.

My story with the schools began in the first school in Trieste. That year, I attended as a student/helper, the next year I helped organize the first S6o Paulo edition of the schools where I also served as helper and lecturer. I was invited to join the group of co-chairs after the second edition of the Schools in Sao Paulo. From my point of view, this type of initiative is unique and helps bridging the gap created by the lack of formal training in Data Science/Open Data related disciplines. Coming from a low-middle income country I experience that gap on a daily basis. Since I decided to join the initiative, I've had the opportunity to teach on several occasions and it has been a very rewarding experience to see students develop and start new collaborations among them.

I'll be giving a seminar on "How to deal with textual data" in January 2020. During this seminar we will cover strategies and tools to manipulate, normalize, and clean textual data. I hope to see you all there!

ALUMNI TESTIMONIES

Dieudonné Niyitanga

I am Dieudonné NIYITANGA a data science enthusiast serving as a research Intern at Bank of Kigali, Rwanda. It was a great pleasure to be among the few selected out of hundreds of applicants on the African continent to attend the first CODATA-RDA School of Research Data Science in Rwanda, Oct-Nov 2018.

Before I joined this school I had been looking into many different universities around the world to gain practical skills. I knew I wanted to study in a data science program or to attend workshop or school in data science, but I also wanted to experience interacting research in the area of the data science. This school enabled me to achieve my dream and gain real world experience in a range of topics, such as R programming, machine learning and artificial neural networks.

This event was a unique opportunity for me to gain knowledge and insight I need to solve daily challenges and to help me contribute to the overall goals of my institution as a researcher. The knowledge and skills that I acquired were immediately applicable to my projects, particular on research data management, data visualisation and machine learning techniques. The teaching and support I received during CODATA School was of very high quality, and I would recommend the schools to all researchers. I am thankful to CODATA-RDA for providing the schools to enhance my skills in data science.

Ola Karrar

In Sudan data science is a brand new domain and to find a local community and support it was a little bit hard. I was advised by my Doctor at the university to apply to the Summer School in Trieste, Italy 2017 as he was exposed to global networks in addition to his knowledge of my interest in the field. I applied to join the school and was lucky to get accepted to attend the CODATA/RDA summer schools.

I believe when joining such an educational program at the beginning it is the hardest part to get first acceptance and letting the community know about you. I always try to spread awareness to my community about how important it is to benefit from such experiences and to give back as it opens new doors for future generations to engage in these programs and networks.

The Summer School expanded my networks with researchers from different

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analysis skills sets needed in their studies. Furthermore, the schools helped me to build strong relationships with the schools' instructors, for example, after I returned from the school, I collaborated with Dr. Louise Bezuidenhout on a research project on the effect of sanctions on the open science movement in Sudan. We succeeded to secure a fund from the University of Oxford that helped us in return to conduct many awareness workshops in Sudan about open science as well as publishing a paper titled: "[Economic sanctions and academia: Overlooked impact and long-term consequences](#)".

I strongly recommend everyone to join the CODATA/RDA summer schools community as it opens doors for early career researchers and helps them build lifelong relationships.

Best wishes to everyone for a peaceful and safe festive season.

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dataschools@codata.org

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